

Subdivision and Roads Layout with Drafting Outputs for Precinct 13, Kings Forest Development

Independent Capstone Project

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Revision Number: 1

0.1 Version Control Table

Revision Number	Date	Description of Change
Rev 0	1 Sep 2025	Original submission
Rev 1	12 Sep 2025	<p>Document Change: <i>Project Scope and Drafting Method and Output Report are compiled into this final report. Drafting Method and Output Report is renamed to Method and Output Report. Addition of revision header and page number. Logo used in drawings, to represent the author, is inserted into the header as well.</i></p> <p>Application of Peer Reviewer’s suggestions including: Section 1 - <i>Addition of cover page, clarifying proper version and version control table, implementation of sections numbering system, addition of drawing outputs scale and sizes note, changing of drawing numbers for clarity, addition of KFD-000 as the drawing set’s cover page, and an addition of a purpose statement.</i> Section 2 - <i>Table and Figure captions and numbering consistency enforced, acronym use defined at the start (for WSUD) and attached vector-based pdf for the drawing outputs with the new drawing numbers.</i></p>

0.2 Purpose Statement

The purpose of this independent capstone project is to demonstrate professional-level drafting, design, and project management competencies through the preparation of a subdivision and road layout project. This work has been undertaken outside the mandatory requirements of the Advanced Diploma of Civil Construction Design, to show alignment with the expectations of a Civil Engineering Draftsperson in practice.

This capstone report compiles the Project Scope and the Method and Output Report, together with the drawing outputs, as a consolidated record of the work produced. It provides a basis for peer review and academic commendation, and serves as evidence of the author’s readiness to contribute to professional drafting and design tasks in the civil construction industry. The design and drawings in this project are not intended for construction or council submissions.

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1.0 Project Scope

1.1 Project Title

Subdivision and Roads Layout with Drafting Outputs for Precinct 13, Kings Forest Development.

1.2 Project Overview

This project demonstrates the preparation of conceptual subdivision drafting outputs for Precinct 13 of the Kings Forest Development, Tweed Shire, NSW. The drawings were produced to showcase the technical precision required for effective communication in line with the Department of Transport and Main Roads' (TMR) Drafting and Design Presentation Standards Manual (DDPSM) Volume 2, Chapter 1. The subdivision layout was prepared using LEDA's Kings Forest Development Code while the roads layout was prepared using accessible design criteria from relevant national (Austroads) and local council (Tweed Shire Council) standards, with the primary focus on drafting practices rather than engineering design validation.

1.3 Project Objective

The objective of this project is to demonstrate drafting competency in the preparation of concept-phase subdivision drawings. A high-level subdivision layout was developed using AutoCAD, Civil 3D, and QGIS to showcase the integration of GIS and CAD tools. The aim is to produce drawings that achieve industry-standard precision and clarity, highlighting drafting as the core professional skill.

1.4 Scope of Work

1.4.1 Location

1. Precinct 13, South of Village Centre and enclosed by precinct 14, as outlined in the Kings Forest Concept Plan. Kings Forest, Tweed Shire, New South Wales.
2. The approximate area of the location chosen is 158,451 square metres.
3. Primary land use is intended to be residential development according to the precinct plan.

1.4.2 Inclusions

The key inclusions of this project are:

1. Drawing for locality plan and drawing list.
 - a. Identification of site boundary and project location.

- b. Background context to show the extent of the project and its relationship to the surrounding area.
 2. Drawing for constraint mapping.
 - a. General environmental constraints to illustrate the extent of developable land for the subdivision layout.
 3. Subdivision Layout (multi-sheet working plan)
 - a. Conceptual subdivision layout with generated parcels bordered by alignments.
 - b. Conceptual road layout including alignments, reserves, curve radii, and basic line markings.
 - c. Marginal overlapping plan information to demonstrate sheet weaving across the documentation set.
 - d. Road hierarchy applied according to the Kings Forest Development Code (KFDC).
 - e. Road reserves referenced to Tweed Shire Council D1 and KFDC Hierarchy.
 - f. Conceptual road design referenced to Austroads design criteria within Civil 3D.
 - g. Lot allocation according to KFDC minimum dimensional controls.
 4. Drawing for an annotated longitudinal plan.
 - a. Longitudinal profile for the major connector alignment, showing both the existing surface and a design profile for comparison.
 - b. Working surface generated in Civil 3D from publicly accessible geographic data.
 - c. Longitudinal plan designed based on Austroad's design criteria for profiles in Civil 3D.
 5. Drawing for an intersection layout.
 - a. Intersection of the major connector and a local street, demonstrating kerb return radii and integration of different road types.
 - b. Kerb return radii obtained from Tweed Shire Council's D1 Road Design.
 - c. Indicative line markings for presentation purposes only.
 6. Typical Cross Sections
 - a. Three representative road types and their cross sections.
 - b. Two kerb cross sections as applied within the typical roads.
 7. Services and Easements Layout (rough draft)
 - a. Indicative location of services and easements with respect to road and property boundaries.

1.4.3 Limitations

1. This project concludes at the preparation of subdivision drafting outputs and does not represent a formal engineering design or a council-endorsed submission. The drawings are prepared for demonstration of design and drafting competencies only.
2. Constraints and overlays were mapped based on relevant and appropriate planning assessments. However, further environmental assessments were not conducted.
3. Road alignments, profiles, and cross sections were prepared in accordance with council standards for demonstration purposes only, without engineering approval.
4. Typical drawing lists for conceptual phase projects often span the full extent of works with multiple sheets. In this project, drawings were limited to representative outputs to demonstrate

drafting capability. Only the major alignment working plan was prepared as a multi-sheet series, to showcase competency in weaving sheets across an alignment.

1.4.4 Exclusions

The following tasks are excluded from this project:

1. Engineer-approved design of road alignments, profiles, intersections and linemarking.
2. Hydrological analysis including flow calculations, hydrological modelling, and stormwater system design.
3. Structural design including structural capacity checks, pavement design, and geotechnical investigations.
4. Landforming calculations including cut/fill balancing and earthworks optimisation beyond surface smoothing for drafting purposes.
5. Detailed public utility plan such as full utility service sizing, coordination, and conflict analysis.

These exclusions do not negate the importance of these considerations in a full conceptual phase project. Rather, they acknowledge the boundaries of an independent capstone.

1.4.5 Software and Tools

The software and tools used for this project are:

1. AutoCAD 2024
2. Civil 3D 2024
3. QGIS
4. TMR AutoCAD Customisation Bundle
5. Civil 3D Country Kits for Australia & New Zealand for 2024 by Autodesk
6. Kings Forest Development Code and Tweed Shire Council Development Control Plan, Development Design Specifications, & Standard Drawings.
7. Drafting and Design Presentation Standards Manual, Department of Transport and Main Roads, Queensland Government

1.4.6 Timeline

As per project work breakdown structure:

Phase	Period
Project Preparation	1 July to 15 July
Site Analysis	16 July to 25 July
Subdivision Design	26 July to 10 August
Drawing Preparations	11 August to 24 August

Finalisation and Reporting	25 August to 1 September
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1.4.7 Outputs

Drawing number series based on inclusion	Size	Scale
KFD-000 Cover Page and Locality	A1	1:2500
KDF-100 Constraint Mapping	A1	1:2500
KDF-200 Subdivision Layout	A1	1:2000 for overview, 1:500
KDF-300 Alignments Plan	A1	1:250
KDF-400 Longitudinal Plan	A1	1:500
KFD-500 Intersections Layout	A1	1:200
KDF-600 Road Cross Section	A1	1:100
KDF-700 Kerb Cross Sections	A1	1:100
KDF-800 Services and Easements (schematic diagram)	A1	1:10

1.5 Advising Engineers

1. Hilbert Merin Libres, Environmental Engineer, Senior Air Quality Engineer in Trinity Consultants Australia
 - Providing project guidance and technical validation.
2. Zain Chamadia, Civil Engineer, Civil Construction Design Instructor in Valley International College
 - Providing technical review on design and drafting.

1.6 Peer Reviewers

1. Nathaniel Von Borja, Civil Engineer

2.0 Method & Output Report

This section ties the context and methodology of the outputs produced. Drawing outputs produced from this report can be referred to in section 2.9 Appendix. The outputs in this report are prepared with a conceptual design level, with the primary aim of demonstrating engineering decisions, drafting methods, and competency in AutoCAD and Civil 3D. The context analysis for constraints was undertaken to show appreciation of their impact on the available developable site. Furthermore, it was made to demonstrate the capability of data gathering and mapping to support a project's design team. The output drawings are not construction-ready drawings, and do not substitute for detailed engineering design.

For drafting and presentation, this project aligns its drawing style with the Queensland Department of Transport and Main Roads (TMR) Drafting and Design Presentation Standards Manual to ensure outputs are consistent with local industry precision and clarity. Furthermore, each drawing was produced to portray a clear visual understanding of the project site and subdivision layout, focusing on drafting accuracy, presentation, and compliance. The TMR customisation bundle for AutoCAD was installed with AutoCAD Civil 3D version 2024 to enable the drawings to be produced under the appropriate style seamlessly.

2.1 Site Identification

Precinct 13 is situated within the Kings Forest urban release area, located in the northern region of New South Wales under the jurisdiction of Tweed Shire Council. The Kings Forest development is a large-scale, masterplanned community comprising multiple precincts designated for staged residential, commercial, and mixed-use development.

According to the Precinct Plan from the Kings Forest Development Plan, Precinct 13 is identified as a low-density residential precinct positioned within the southern half of the development area. It is geographically nested within the broader boundary of Precinct 14, as defined in the Precinct Plan (LEDA Holdings, n.d) which can be seen in Figure 2.1.1.

Figure 2.1.1. Precinct Plan of Kings Forest Development Plan.

Figure 2.1.2 illustrates the actual site boundary of Precinct 13 in relation to its surrounding. This spatial context is used to guide all further works such as constraint mapping, alignment preliminary design, or topography mapping. Figure 2.1.2 was developed using Civil 3D. Civil 3D’s coordinate reference system (CRS) was set to MGA/20-56 with the horizontal datum being GDA 2020. This choice was preferred for this project because GDA 2020 is the local industry’s legal datum.

First, cadastral boundaries were obtained from SDT Explorer, specifically the NSW Land Parcel and Property Theme multiCRS dataset. This dataset supports multiCRS so it was downloaded with GDA2020 MGA-56 as an ESRI shape file. This file was imported into Civil 3D to be the anchor points for georeferencing the Precinct Plan. After manually georeferencing the Precinct Plan to known boundaries, that border of Precinct 13 was digitally traced, enclosing the project site. Along with the border, the alignment of the connector road was traced as well as it follows the on-going development of connector alignments that LEDA has designed. An Aerial Map in Civil 3D was used as the background for better visualisation. This output is the basis of KFD-100 Site Identification and Drawing List, showing the locality and drawing list of the project’s drawings.

Figure 2.1.2. Precinct 13 Boundary (blue line) with cadastral boundaries (green lines) on an Aerial Image and Precinct Plan as the background.

Surface Setup & Working Base

The dataset for the topography and surface was sourced from the Elevation Information System, Geoscience Australia (ELVIS) platform. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of Australia derived from LiDAR 5 Metre Grid dataset of the whole Precinct 13, and a considerable offset region, has a CRS of GDA 94. However, ordering the data through ELVIS had the option to transform the data. As such, it was downloaded in TIFF format with MGA-56 (GDA2020) as its CRS and then imported into Civil 3D to generate a continuous surface model across the project site.

The downloaded TIFF file was unreadable by Civil 3D directly so it was first imported into QGIS to be turned into points and the elevation attribute was assigned as each points' Z-values. The layer was exported as a shapefile then imported into Civil 3D, covering Precinct 13 and its offset regions. A Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) surface was generated from the file and it was clipped to the precinct boundary.

2.2 Physical Constraint Mapping

For constraints, QGIS was used to map the datasets of each relevant constraint. The precinct boundary from KFD-100 was imported as a shapefile with the MGA/20-56 CRS to be used as the reference in QGIS – with the project's CRS being locked into EPSG: 7856 (MGA/20-56). Locking the QGIS project CRS to EPSG:7856 allows the datasets with different CRS to be mapped appropriately.

After reviewing the mapping, the impact of influencing constraints were drawn in KFD-200 - Constraints Mapping to visualise the constraints in the precinct.

Contaminated land

A preliminary contamination screening was conducted using the NSW Planning Portal Spatial Viewer, specifically referencing the SEPP No 33 - Hazardous and Offensive Development 1992 dataset. This dataset identifies sites across New South Wales associated with hazardous or offensive industries and land uses that may lead to contamination risks. No flagged industrial sites, symbols, or hazard zones appear within or near Precinct 13. The absence of icons or overlays in the dataset indicates that the area is not associated with any activities regulated under SEPP No 33. This supports the assumption that the precinct and its surrounding lands have no known historical use involving potentially contaminating industries such as chemical storage, manufacturing, or waste disposal.

While this preliminary assessment suggests low contamination risk, a detailed site investigation (DSI) may still be warranted during detailed design or construction phases to ensure compliance with the Contaminated Land Management Act 1997 and to confirm the absence of subsurface pollutants.

Land with risk of land slip or subsidence

Identification of landslip or subsidence risk requires a formal geotechnical investigation and site-specific modelling. This capstone delivers drafting outputs only; therefore no geotechnical hazard mapping is included. Any future development will require geotechnical assessment in accordance with council and state guidelines.

Bushfire Risk

Precinct 13 is identified as falling within Bushfire Prone Land Category 3 (Vegetation Buffer) according to the NSW Bushfire Prone Land 2021 dataset, which was downloaded via the NSW Planning Portal and reviewed in QGIS. This can be seen in Figure 2.2.1 for the overlay analysis, with the legend shown in Table 2.2.1.

Colour	Classification
Red	Category 1
Yellow	Category 2
Orange	Category 3
Light Yellow	Vegetation Buffer

Table 2.2.1. Bushfire risk overlay analysis legend.

Although Category 3 represents a lower hazard intensity compared to Categories 1 and 2, its presence still triggers bushfire design obligations under Planning for Bushfire Protection - A Guide for

Land Use Planners, Fire Authorities, Developers and Home Owners (NSW Rural Fire Service, 2001) and Section A5 of the Tweed Shire Development Control Plan (DCP).

Figure 2.2.1. NSW Bushfire Prone Land overlay from Planning Hazard Layer on Precinct 13 in QGIS.

To comply with these guidelines, a conservative 20 m Asset Protection Zone (APZ) has been applied around the entire precinct boundary, based on minimum distance requirements in Table 4.1 of the Tweed Shire DCP. This has been applied in KFD-200 via offsetting the precinct boundary inwards by 20 metres which is to be filled by a hatch.

Threatened species, population or ecological communities or their habitats

Subdivision development within Precinct 13 is subject to biodiversity protection obligations under the Biodiversity Conservation Act 2016 and the Environmental Planning and Assessment Act 1979. Specifically, any proposed subdivision works must consider potential impacts on threatened species, populations, or ecological communities, and their habitats.

Although a formal ecological assessment under Section 5A of the EP&A Act has not been conducted as part of this project, mapped biodiversity values have been reviewed using the publicly accessible Biodiversity Values Map (non-EPI) dataset, made available through the NSW Planning Portal and visualised in QGIS. As shown in Figure 2.2.2, large areas surrounding Precinct 13 are classified as high-value biodiversity zones, particularly to the north and east of the site. However, the precinct boundary itself does not directly overlap with these mapped zones.

Figure 2.2.2. Biodiversity Values mapping near Precinct 13, using NSW Planning Portal (non-EPI) dataset in QGIS.

Due to the lack of direct overlap and in the absence of specialist ecological input, no constraint was mapped in KFD-200.

Coastal lands

A small portion of the southern boundary of Precinct 13 falls within land mapped as Coastal Land under the NSW State Environmental Planning Policy (Resilience and Hazards) 2021 – as mapped out in Figure 2.2.3. This designation identifies areas with coastal character or sensitivity to erosion, scenic impact, and ecological disturbance.

Figure 2.2.3 Overlay of mapped Coastal Land zone on Precinct 13 using SEPP Resilience and Hazards 2021 dataset (NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure 2023).

The mapping data was obtained via REST Web Service from the SEPP RH - Coastal Management Areas dataset published on the NSW SEED Portal and overlaid onto the Precinct 13 boundary using QGIS. The area of overlap is relatively minor but has design implications. In accordance with good planning practice and to minimize development impact, the conceptual lot allocation excluded this area. To map this in KFD-200, the layer was exported as an ESRI shape file and imported into Civil 3D. The overlap was then bounded with a polyline then a hatch was placed.

Coastal Wetlands

Although Precinct 13 does not intersect any mapped SEPP 14 wetlands, a considerable amount of area, especially in the northern half, falls within the 100-metre buffer zone for adjacent wetlands under the SEPP Resilience and Hazards 2021. This was confirmed through mapping via the REST Web Service using the SEPP RH - Coastal Management Areas dataset in QGIS. The buffer zone overlaps significantly with the developable area of Precinct 13, especially on the northern side as shown in Figure 2.2.4. While this does not restrict development on the site, it is recommended that the detailed design is sensitive to these coastal wetlands – controlling the quality of water discharges.

Figure 2.2.4. Mapped buffer zone for Coastal Wetlands intersecting with northern and southeastern boundaries of Precinct 13 (NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure 2023).

Littoral Rainforests

Using the SEPP Resilience and Hazards 2021 - Littoral Rainforests dataset via the NSW REST web service, the closest mapped Littoral Rainforest patch and its associated proximity buffer were visualised in QGIS and compared with the Precinct 13 location. As shown in Figure 2.2.5, the nearest patch is located well southeast of Precinct 13, and there is no spatial overlap between Precinct 13 and either the core rainforest zone (solid green) or its regulated proximity area (hashed zone). This does not restrict any works relevant for this project on the site.

Figure 2.2.5. Mapped proximity of Littoral Rainforest and Proximity Area with no overlap to Precinct 13 using SEPP Resilience and Hazards 2021 dataset (NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure 2023).

Koala Habitat

Precinct 13 is not directly classified as Core Koala Habitat, based on the Core Koala Habitat - NSW Koala Strategy (Koala Habitat Information Base) dataset published on the NSW Spatial Collaboration Portal and reviewed in QGIS. However, the precinct is entirely surrounded by mapped koala habitat areas, particularly to the east, south, and west. This proximity implies a high likelihood of koala movement near or through the site. This does not restrict any works relevant for this project. However, the high likelihood may require additional proper vehicular control measures in the detailed design, such as koala warning traffic signs. Figure 2.2.6 illustrates the mapped koala habitat areas surrounding the Precinct 13 boundary.

Figure 2.2.6. Mapped Core Koala Habitat areas surrounding Precinct 13, using NSW Koala Strategy dataset in QGIS.

Significant vegetation

Although a formal vegetation condition assessment has not been undertaken as part of this project, the mapped Biodiversity Values (non-EPI) dataset was reviewed within QGIS using high-resolution satellite imagery sourced via the AusMap plugin. Figure 2.2.11 presents the overlay of this dataset with Precinct 13, highlighting vegetation zones of potential significance based on visual indicators. This does not restrict any works relevant for this project on the site.

Figure 2.2.7. Overlay of Biodiversity Values Map and satellite imagery for Precinct 13, using Google Satellite base from AusMap Plugin in QGIS.

Acid sulphate soils

For Acid Sulfate Soil classification, the NSW Planning Portal Spatial Viewer was accessed. The Acid Sulfate Soil layer was chosen under the protection group and the Kings Forest site was selected to enable site highlighting for classification context. Figure 2.2.8 shows the Spatial Viewer screenshot of the Kings Forest with the Acid Sulfate Soil classification layer. In the figure, the layer has class labels and Kings Forest is outlined by the yellow dashed lines in its borders. Kings Forest was selected by referring to its lot label, 11/-/DP1270901 which was obtained by referring to Lot Labels in the NSW SDT Explorer.

Figure 2.2.8. NSW Planning Portal Spatial Viewer output highlighting Kings Forest and surrounding ASS classifications.

Due to absence of mapped ASS data directly within Precinct 13 (south west edge of Kings Forest) in the NSW Planning Portal Spatial viewer, the classification was conservatively assumed based on the adjacent mapped regions. Surrounding land around the southwestern edge of Kings Forest development shows Class 2 and Class 3 zones, as defined under EPI Acid Sulfate Soils (State Government of NSW and NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure, 2018). The classifications and description under EPI Acid Sulfate Soils are shown in Table 2.2.2.

Classification	Description
Class 1	Acid sulfate soils in a class 1 area are likely to be found on and below the natural ground surface.
Class 2	Acid sulfate soils in a class 2 area are likely to be found below the natural ground surface.
Class 3	Acid sulfate soils in a class 3 area are likely to be found beyond 1 metre below the natural ground surface.
Class 4	Acid sulfate soils in a class 4 area are likely to be found beyond 2 metres below the natural ground surface.

Class 5	Acid sulfate soils are not typically found in Class 5 areas. Areas classified as Class 5 are located within 500 metres on adjacent class 1,2,3 or 4 land.
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Table 2.2.2. EPI Acid Sulfate Soils classification.

Based on proximity, topographic similarity, and hydrological conditions, Class 2 was selected to conservatively inform design precautions.

In accordance with Section 5.4 of the Tweed Shire Council DCP, disturbance of potential acid sulfate soils must be minimised, and if disturbance is unavoidable, an Acid Sulfate Soils Management Plan must be prepared in accordance with EPA guidelines (refer to Clause 35 of the TLEP 2000).

Heritage or cultural items of Aboriginal or European origin

Although a formal heritage investigation has not been conducted for this capstone project, publicly available spatial datasets from the NSW Planning Portal have been reviewed. The Heritage Map dataset (Environmental Planning Instrument - Heritage) was accessed via the Spatial Viewer and visualised in QGIS to determine any mapped heritage constraints relevant to Precinct 13.

As shown in Figure 2.2.9, there are no recorded heritage or cultural items within or immediately adjacent to Precinct 13. This does not restrict any works relevant for this project on the site.

Figure 2.2.9. Mapped heritage constraints near Precinct 13, using NSW Planning Portal (EPI - Heritage) dataset in QGIS.

Constraint Mapping

The final constraints mapped in KFD-200 were the Coastal Lands and the APZ buffer as it directly impacts available land use

2.3 Road Hierarchy and Alignments

The road layout for Precinct 13 adopts the KFDC Stage 1 Road Hierarchy Plan which is shown in Figure 2.3.1.

Figure 2.3.1. KFDC Road Hierarchy Plan.

Within the precinct, the primary road connection is identified in the Kings Forest Development Code (KFDC) as the E-Type Low Volume Neighbourhood Connector Road, intended to run longitudinally through the development area – acting as the backbone of the subdivision. However, the KFDC reserve width specification for this category does not align directly with the Tweed Shire Council Development Design Specification D1 (TSC D1).

To ensure compliance with TSC D1 standards, the E-Type road was considered as a “Wider Access Street with Bus Route”, which maintains the intended neighbourhood connector function but provides consistency in reserve width, cross-section, and design controls for bus access.

Supporting this hierarchy, the KFDC identifies F-Type Access Streets for lot frontage and local circulation. In practice, these will be adopted as “Access Streets with 7.5 m Carriageway” in accordance with TSC D1, ensuring efficient lot servicing while meeting Council’s standard design requirements.

This adjustment ensures that all roads in the subdivision are both consistent with KFDC intent and compliant with Council’s endorsed road design standards.

While there is no detailed design of roads in this project, the type of roads have easily accessible values for a few of its parameters. Table 2.3.1 shows the road parameters based on TSC D1 Road Design and KFDC.

Conceptual Design Parameters		
Parameter	E-Type Connector	F-Type Access Street
Speed Limit	50 kilometres per hour	50 kilometres per hour
Maximum Uninterrupted Length	250 m	250 m
Frontage Discouraged	Yes	No

Table 2.3.1. Road parameters based on TSC D1 Road Design and KFDC.

Alignments

The alignments were developed using Civil 3D’s alignment creation tools while using the design criteria xml Austroads Min Radius Tables_ANZ_2016 from Civil 3D Country Kits for Australia & New Zealand. This ensures a compliant design based on relevant constraints such as passing sight distance and stopping sight distance. The design speed of the alignments were according to the conceptual design parameters in Table 2.3.1, setting the speed limit for all alignments to 50 kilometres per hour with a maximum uninterrupted length of 250 metres.

The concept of creating the alignment layout starts with the E-Type connector road from the road hierarchy. That road is shown in both the Precinct Plan and the Road Hierarchy Map.

The E-Type connector was digitally traced from the georeferenced Precinct Plan. However, due to the drawings being scaled and not technically specific, the E-Type alignment was drawn in a way that would nest itself in the APZ buffer as much as possible, allowing the property boundaries to hug the APZ buffer. This allows a higher available land for development.

The F-Type perimeter was drawn perpendicular from the E type connector, heading east. Then it reorients south, allowing the reserve width to align itself on the APZ buffer. As it reaches the south of the precinct, it turns to the west allowing the reserve width to not enroach in the mapped coastal land region. Finally, it turns northwest – joining the E-Type road.

Five F-Type access street “legs” were drawn spanning from the E-Type connector to the F-Type perimeter, dividing the large block of land inside the two main alignments for smaller lots and more frontage access.

The KFD-400 series demonstrates the drafting of alignment, specifically the E-Type.

2.4 Longitudinal Profile

The longitudinal profile was developed by taking the profile of the alignments with respect to the site's surface and drawing a design profile using tangents with curves. The design profiles were subject to Austroad's 2016 design criteria from the downloaded ANZ Civil 3D kit – checking desirable minimum K's with 2.0 reaction time, ensuring design compliance with stopping sight distance, passing sight distance, and headlight sight distance. Further detailed design is recommended to account for the minimum kerb grade which is to be a minimum of 0.3% according to TSC D1 Road Design.

The KFD-500 demonstrates the drafting of a longitudinal plan of the F-Type 4 alignment.

2.5 Intersections

Where alignments have intersected, intersections were created using the intersection wizard allowing a 10-metre kerb return radius as specified in TSC D1 as the minimum default kerb return radius. It was not increased because intersections and sharp turns were intended to have a design speed of 20 kilometres per hour as intended slow points.

The KFD-500 demonstrates the drafting of an intersection layout of the northern intersection of E-Type and F-Type perimeter.

2.6 Lot Layout

Lot layout commenced when road alignments were designed. Each resulting block was assigned to a dedicated site for parcel creation, allowing clearer grouping and easier lot labelling. The lot layout prioritised assigning frontages into F-Type roads while the minimum dimensions were taken from KFDC, basing it on the dimensions of traditional dwelling lots.

For block one and eight, the lot frontages were to the F-Type perimeter road with the rear of the lots facing north and west, respectively. For blocks two and three, the frontages were the same but the rears faced the E-Type road. For blocks four to seven, the lot frontages were mostly on the F-Type legs with each block having lots' rears against each other.

This lot layout ensures frontage prioritisation to F-Type roads to minimise interruption of the E-Type connector, while rear boundaries were positioned either against opposing lots or external boundaries, maintaining consistency with KFDC traditional dwelling lot requirements. This was used as the basis for the parcel generation in Civil 3D. It was ensured that area of mapped constraints were excluded from the development of lots

The KFD-300 series demonstrates the drafting of the subdivision layout including an overview and close up versions of the subdivided blocks.

2.7 Typical Cross Sections

Four typical road cross sections were developed to cater all alignments in the subdivision. The E-Type alignment has two types while F-Type alignments have two – separated by different cross sections based on whether there will be frontages on the adjacent property boundary. The road cross sections were based on Tweed Shire Council’s standard drawing for roadworks to ensure design compliance, specifically SD001 and SD004. It is either a combination of a water sensitive urban design (WSUD) and non-WSUD cross section or a complete non-WSUD cross section. The kerbs for the cross section were adopted from SD007, providing a barrier kerb and gutter for non-WSUD kerbs and a flush edging strip for WSUD kerbs.

The **E-Type – inside the E-Type and F-Type perimeter intersections** cross section is a combination of a non-WSUD half and a WSUD half. The alignment flows from north to south. Thus, the WSUD half is on the right side with a continuous footpath allowing through-precinct pedestrian access. The left side is non-WSUD to ensure safety of local pedestrians.

The **E-Type – outside the E-Type and F-Type perimeter intersections** cross section has WSUD on both sides with its left cross section weaving seamlessly to the F-Type perimeter’s WSUD side.

The **F-Type perimeter** cross section involves a combination of non-WSUD and WSUD halves as well. The F-Type perimeter road flows from north to south as well. As such, the combination cross section has the WSUD on the left side.

The **F-Type legs** adopt a full non-WSUD design.

These road cross sections create a boundary of swale around the developed site of Precinct 13 to adopt a WSUD subdivision and roads layout.

The KFD-700 demonstrates the drafting of these typical road cross sections while KFD-800 for the kerb cross sections.

2.8 Service and Easements

The placement of services and easements was guided by Section 5.9 of the KFDC. The detailed design of a public utility plant drawing requires heavy cooperation with utility companies and heavy calculations for stormwater, water conveyance, and sewerage infrastructure layout. As such, KFD-900 instead shows a schematic diagram of the location of services and easements.

2.9 Appendix

<i>DRAWING NUMBER</i>	<i>DWG FILE LOCATION</i>	<i>PDF FILE LOCATION</i>
<i>KFD-000</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD_001\KFD001.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-100</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD_002\KFD002.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-200</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD MAIN\KFDMAIN.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-300</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD MAIN\KFDMAIN.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-400</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD MAIN\KFDMAIN.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-500</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD MAIN\KFDMAIN.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-600</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD_007\KFD007.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-700</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD_008\KFD008.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>
<i>KFD-800</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\KFD_009\KFD009.dwg</i>	<i>Capstone_2025_KingsForest\03_Drawings\PDFs</i>

Table 2.9.1. Drawing File Locations.

CONCEPT ONLY
13 September 2025

REFERENCE POINT
EASTING: 168976.4896
NORTHING: 2093640.3731

KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT PRECINCT 13 SUBDIVISION AND ROAD LAYOUT – CONCEPTUAL

Drawing Number	Revision	Date	Series Number	Drawing Description
KFD-000	B	12/9/2025	1	COVER PAGE AND LOCALITY
KFD-100	B	12/9/2025	1	CONSTRAINT MAPPING
KFD-200	B	12/9/2025	1	SUBDIVISION LAYOUT OVERVIEW
KFD-201	B	12/9/2025	2	SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCKS 1-2
KFD-202	B	12/9/2025	3	SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCKS 3-4
KFD-203	B	12/9/2025	4	SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCK 5-6
KFD-204	B	12/9/2025	5	SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCK 7-8
KFD-300	B	12/9/2025	1	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 0 - 160
KFD-301	B	12/9/2025	2	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 160 - 300
KFD-302	B	12/9/2025	3	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 300 - 440
KFD-303	B	12/9/2025	4	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 440 - 620
KFD-304	B	12/9/2025	5	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 620 - 760
KFD-305	B	12/9/2025	6	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 760 - 900
KFD-306	B	12/9/2025	7	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 900 - 980
KFD-307	B	12/9/2025	8	ALIGNMENT PLAN CH 980 - 1048
KFD-400	B	12/9/2025	1	LONGITUDINAL PLAN
KFD-500	B	12/9/2025	1	INTERSECTION LAYOUT
KFD-600	B	12/9/2025	1	TYPICAL CROSS SECTION ROAD
KFD-700	B	12/9/2025	1	TYPICAL CROSS SECTION KERB
KFD-800	B	12/9/2025	1	LOCATION OF EASEMENT AND SERVICES SCHEMATIC

TOTAL NUMBER OF DRAWINGS = 20

LOCALITY

Last Modified: 13 Sep 2025 11:50am XREFS: -

F	Associated Job Nos		Survey Data		Scales 1:2500 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13 COVER PAGE AND LOCALITY				
	Auxiliary Drg Nos		Horiz. Datum	GDA 2020		CTL CHGE				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)				
C			Horiz. Grid	MGA Zone 56	Reference Points				Job No.					
B			Height Datum	AHD	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Contract No.
A	CONCEPT ONLY		Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				Drawing No. KFD-000					
Revisions/Descriptions			Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title		Date		Through Chainage from				Series Number 1 of 1			

CONCEPT ONLY
12 September 2025

LEGEND

COASTAL LAND CONSTRAINT	
APZ BUFFER CONSTRAINT	

Last Modified :- Sep 12, 2025 - 11:00pm XREFS :-

F		Associated Job Nos		Survey Data		Scales		TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL		KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13			
E				Horiz. Datum GDA 2020		1:2500 @ A1				CONSTRAINT MAPPING			
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos		GDA 2020 MGA Zone 56		<i>CTL CHGE</i>				Job No.	
C				Height Datum		AHD		Reference Points		ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)		Contract No.	
B				Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise		Preceding RP		SIGNATORY FULL NAME		Drawing No. KFD-100	
A		CONCEPT ONLY		Date				Dist. to start of job (km)		No.		Series Number	
		Revisions/Descriptions		Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title				From start to end of job		DATE		1 of 1	
								From end to Following RP					
								Through Chainage from					

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:2000 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13					
E				Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				SUBDIVISION LAYOUT					
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	GDA2020		CTL CHGE				OVERVIEW					
C				Horiz. Grid	MGA Zone 56		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
B				Height Datum	AHD	Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	KFD-200 B
A	CONCEPT ONLY	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date	Survey Books	Through Chainage from									Series Number	

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:500 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13					
E				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Datum GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				SUBDIVISION LAYOUT					
D					Horiz. Grid MGA Zone 56		CTL CHGE				BLOCKS 1-2					
C					Height Datum AHD		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
B					Survey Books	Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	KFD-201B
A	CONCEPT ONLY														Series Number	
	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date													

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:500 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL E-TYPE CONNECTOR				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13 SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCKS 3-4					
E				Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		CTL CHGE				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid		GDA2020 MGA Zone 56	Reference Points				SIGNATORY FULL NAME				
C					Height Datum		AHD	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	No.		DATE
B					Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				KFD-202 B					
A	CONCEPT ONLY						Through Chainage from				Series Number 3 of 5					
	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date													

CONCEPT ONLY
13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:500 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL E-TYPE CONNECTOR CTL CHGE	KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13 SUBDIVISION LAYOUT BLOCKS 5-6																			
E				Horiz. Datum	GDA2020																						
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid MGA Zone 56																						
C				Height Datum	AHD																						
B				Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise	Reference Points	ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)																			
A	CONCEPT ONLY	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date				<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Preceding RP</th> <th>Dist. to start of job (km)</th> <th>From start to end of job</th> <th>From end to Following RP</th> <th>Following RP</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP						<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>ENG. AREA</th> <th>SIGNATORY FULL NAME</th> <th>No.</th> <th>DATE</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE					
Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP																							
ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE																								
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>CAD FILES</td> <td colspan="8"></td> <td>Series Number</td> <td>4</td> <td>of</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </table>										CAD FILES									Series Number	4	of	5					
CAD FILES									Series Number	4	of	5															

KFD-203B

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data		Scales	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13						
					Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		1:250 @ A1		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				ALIGNMENT PLAN				
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid	GDA2020	Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise	CTL CHGE				CH 0 - 160						
C					Height Datum	AHD		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)						
B				Survey Books				Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Job No.	
A	CONCEPT ONLY																Contract No.	
	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date														Drawing No. KFD-300B	
CAD FILES																	Series Number	1 of 8

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data		Scales	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13						
					Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				ALIGNMENT PLAN						
E				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid	GDA2020	1:250 @ A1	CTL CHGE				CH 620 - 760				Job No.		
D					Height Datum	AHD		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)						
C				Survey Books	Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Contract No.	
B																		
A	CONCEPT ONLY																Series Number	
Revisions/Descriptions			Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date														5 of 8

CAD FILES

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F			Associated Job Nos	Survey Data		Scales	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13					
				Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				ALIGNMENT PLAN					
E			Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid	MGA Zone 56	1:250 @ A1	CTL CHGE				CH 760 - 900				Job No.	
D				Height Datum	AHD		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
C			Survey Books	Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise			Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Contract No.
B																
A	CONCEPT ONLY														Series Number	
Revisions/Descriptions		Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title		Date										6 of 8		

CAD FILES

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:250 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13					
E				Horiz. Datum	GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				ALIGNMENT PLAN					
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid		GDA2020	CTL CHGE				CH 900 - 980				
C					MGA Zone 56		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
B				Height Datum	AHD	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Job No.	
A	CONCEPT ONLY			Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				Through Chainage from				Contract No.		
Revisions/Descriptions		Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title		Date	Drawing No. KFD-306 B Series Number 7 of 8											

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:250 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13										
E				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Datum GDA2020		E-TYPE CONNECTOR				ALIGNMENT PLAN										
D					Horiz. Grid MGA Zone 56		CTL CHGE				CH 980 - 1048										
C					Height Datum AHD		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)										
B					Survey Books	Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	SIGNATORY FULL NAME	No.	DATE	Job No.	Contract No.	
A	CONCEPT ONLY			Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date														Drawing No. KFD-307	B	
Revisions/Descriptions								Through Chainage from								Series Number	8	of	8		

CONCEPT ONLY

12 September 2025

VERT. DATA
DATUM 3.00

DESIGN HEIGHT	5.06	5.12	5.19	5.28	5.53	5.80	6.00
NATURAL SURFACE	5.06	5.11	5.09	5.22	5.50	5.93	
CHAINAGE	0.00	35.00	70.00	105.00	140.00	175.00	201.54
HORIZONTAL DATA	STRAIGHT		R-56	STRAIGHT			

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:500 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13				
E				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Datum		F-TYPE 4				LONGITUDINAL PLAN				
D					Horiz. Grid		CTL CHGE								
C					MGA Zone 56		Reference Points				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)				
B					Height Datum					Job No.					
A	CONCEPT ONLY				AHD					Contract No.					
	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date	Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				Drawing No. KFD-400 B					
CAD FILES						Through Chainage from				Series Number 1 of 1					

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:100 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13						
E				Horiz. Datum			TYPICAL CROSS SECTION				JOB No.						
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos	Horiz. Grid		CTL CHGE				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)						
C				Height Datum			Reference Points				SIGNATORY FULL NAME						
B				Survey Books		Dimensions shown in metres except where shown otherwise				No.				DATE			
A	CONCEPT ONLY			Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title		Date		Through Chainage from				Contract No.					
Revisions/Descriptions									Drawing No. KFD-700				Series Number 1 of 1				

CONCEPT ONLY

13 September 2025

F				Associated Job Nos	Survey Data	Scales 1:10 @ A1	TWEED SHIRE COUNCIL				KINGS FOREST DEVELOPMENT, PRECINCT 13 LOCATION OF EASEMENT AND SERVICES SCHEMATIC					
E				Horiz. Datum	Dimensions shown in millimetres except where shown otherwise		CTL CHGE				ENGINEERING CERTIFICATION (RPEQ)					
D				Auxiliary Drg Nos			Horiz. Grid	Reference Points				SIGNATORY FULL NAME				
C							Height Datum	Preceding RP	Dist. to start of job (km)	From start to end of job	From end to Following RP	Following RP	ENG. AREA	No.		DATE
B					Survey Books	Through Chainage from								Contract No.		
A	CONCEPT ONLY													Drawing No. KFD-800		
	Revisions/Descriptions	Signatory: - RPEQ Full Name, Eng. Area and RPEQ No. or - Full Name and Position Title	Date											Series Number 1 of 1		

2.10 References

LEDA Holdings Pty Ltd. (n.d.) Kings Forest Concept Plan and Development Documents. Available at: <https://www.tweed.nsw.gov.au/development-business/land-use-planning-controls/major-housing-developments/kings-forest-development> [Accessed: 15 July 2025].

Geoscience Australia. (2025) ELVIS – Digital Elevation Model (DEM) 5 Metre Grid of Australia derived from LiDAR model. Available at: https://services.ga.gov.au/gis/rest/services/DEM_LiDAR_5m_2025/MapServer [Accessed: 26 August 2025].

NSW Department of Customer Service - Spatial Services 2025, NSW Planning Hazard - Bushfire Prone Land Dataset, NSW Planning Portal Spatial Viewer, viewed August 2025, <https://www.planningportal.nsw.gov.au/spatialviewer>.

NSW Department of Planning and Environment 2025, Biodiversity Values Map (non-EPI), NSW Planning Portal Spatial Data Viewer, viewed August 2025, <https://datasets.seed.nsw.gov.au/dataset/biodiversity-values-map>

NSW Department of Planning and Environment 2025, Environmental Planning Instrument - Heritage (Heritage Map), NSW Planning Portal Spatial Data Viewer, viewed 6 August 2025, <https://www.planningportal.nsw.gov.au/opendata/dataset/environmental-planning-instrument-heritage-her>

NSW Department of Planning and Environment 2022, State Environmental Planning Policy (Resilience and Hazards) 2021 – Environmental Constraints Mapping, SEED NSW, viewed 3 August 2025, <https://datasets.seed.nsw.gov.au/dataset/state-environmental-planning-policy-resilience-and-hazards-2021>

NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure 1992, State Environmental Planning Policy No 33 - Hazardous and Offensive Development 1992, NSW Government, viewed 4 August 2025, <https://www.planningportal.nsw.gov.au/opendata/dataset/sepp-hazardous-offensive-development>.

NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure 2025, Core Koala Habitat – NSW Koala Strategy (Koala Habitat Information Base), NSW Spatial Collaboration Portal, viewed 6 August 2025, <https://portal.spatial.nsw.gov.au/portal/home/item.html?id=4716468a826b45e085ae7b446ec4ec73>

Queensland Department of Transport and Main Roads (TMR). (2020). Drafting and Design Presentation Standards. Brisbane: Queensland Government. Available at:

<https://www.tmr.qld.gov.au/business-industry/Technical-standards-publications/Drafting-and-design-presentation-standards> [Accessed 24 Aug. 2025]

Spatial Services (DCS). (n.d.) NSW Land Parcel Property Theme – MultiCRS. Available at: <https://portal.spatial.nsw.gov.au/portal/home/item.html?id=079705a7798742e6b13b6da2171e5991> [Accessed: 26 August 2025].

State Government of NSW and NSW Department of Planning, Housing and Infrastructure, 2018. EPI Acid Sulfate Soils. [online] NSW Planning Portal - Open Data. Available at: <https://www.planningportal.nsw.gov.au/opendata/dataset/epi-acid-sulfate-soils> [Accessed: 15 July 2025].

Tweed Shire Council. (2023) Development Control Plan. Available at: <https://www.tweed.nsw.gov.au/development-business/land-use-planning-controls/environment-control-plans/development-control-plan> [Accessed: 15 July 2025].

Tweed Shire Council (n.d.). Engineering specifications and standard drawings – Roadworks and streets (SD.001–SD.008). Tweed Shire Council. Available at: Tweed Shire Council website [Accessed: 15 July 2025].

Tweed Shire Council. (2020). Tweed Coastal Creeks Floodplain Risk Management Study and Plan. Available at: <https://www.tweed.nsw.gov.au/files/assets/public/v/1/documents/property-and-rates/floods-and-stormwater/tweed-coastal-creeks-floodplain-risk-management-study.pdf> [Accessed: 18 July 2025].